

INTRODUCING PURPOSES IN WRITING, AUTHENTICITY IN THE WRITING PROCESS, AND GIVING FEEDBACK

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Abstract: This article explores the significance of purpose, authenticity, and feedback in the writing process, emphasizing their interconnected roles in fostering genuine communication. Writing with a clear purpose ensures direction, while authenticity allows writers to express their unique voices. Feedback serves as a vital bridge between the writer's intentions and the reader's understanding, enabling improvement and growth. Drawing insights from philosophical and educational perspectives, this study highlights practical applications of these principles in writing education.

Key Words: writing purpose, authenticity, feedback, writing process, pedagogy.

Introduction

Writing is a versatile tool for human expression, whether to inform, persuade, or simply reflect personal thoughts. In the writing process, understanding one's purpose, remaining authentic, and seeking constructive feedback are essential for creating meaningful and impactful texts. My experience confirms that when I write with clear goals, my work resonates more effectively with readers. This article integrates philosophical and pedagogical insights from thinkers like Fromm, Taylor, and Trilling to provide a deeper understanding of these elements.

Methods

The analysis combines theoretical perspectives with personal reflection. By referencing existentialist philosophy (Fromm, 1942; Park, 2007), historical discourse (Saupe, 2016; Trilling, 1974), and ethics of authenticity (Taylor, 1992), I connect abstract ideas to practical strategies. My own experiences as a writer and educator are woven throughout to illustrate how these principles apply in real-life contexts.

Results

1. Introducing Purposes in Writing

A clear purpose anchors the writing process. Without a defined objective, writing risks becoming unfocused and disconnected. For example, in my own work, I've found that outlining my purpose before starting a project helps me maintain consistency and engage my audience more effectively. Charles Taylor (1992) asserts that alignment between personal values and writing goals creates authenticity and meaning, a principle I strive to implement in every piece I write.¹

In teaching writing, I emphasize helping students articulate their intentions. Whether they aim to inform or persuade, clarity of purpose empowers them to connect with readers and meet their objectives. Achim Saupe's (2016) research supports this, noting that purposeful writing fosters deeper engagement both for the writer and the audience.²

¹ Taylor, Charles (1992). *The Ethics of Authenticity*. Harvard University Press. ISBN 0-674-26863-6.1. № 1 (2023): FAN JURNALI TA'LIM VA MADANIYAT

² Saupe, Achim (2016-12-04). "Authenticity". *Docupedia-Zeitgeschichte*. doi:10.14765/zsf.dok.2.645.v1.

2. Authenticity in the Writing Process

Authenticity is the essence of effective writing. Drawing on Lionel Trilling's (1974) distinction between sincerity and authenticity, I believe writing becomes authentic when the writer's inner voice is expressed without undue external influence. Fromm (1942) similarly underscores the importance of freedom from societal conformity, a sentiment I deeply resonate with.

Authenticity involves embracing vulnerability and rejecting the temptation to mimic others. When I've allowed myself to write honestly, the result has been more compelling, even if imperfect. Authenticity also means allowing room for revision—acknowledging that our first attempts may not fully convey our intentions but refining them until they do.

3. Giving Feedback

Feedback is an indispensable part of writing. However, I've noticed that the way feedback is delivered makes a significant difference in its effectiveness. Constructive feedback that highlights strengths while addressing weaknesses helps me see my work in a new light and motivates me to improve. Park (2007) notes that feedback should not only critique but also nurture the writer's self-awareness and authenticity, a principle I wholeheartedly endorse.³

As a teacher, I strive to give feedback that is both specific and encouraging. For instance, instead of simply pointing out grammatical errors, I guide students to understand how those corrections improve clarity and alignment with their purpose. Feedback, when framed positively, empowers writers to take ownership of their work rather than feeling discouraged by criticism.

Discussion

Purpose, authenticity, and feedback are deeply interconnected elements of the writing process. My own experiences align with Erich Fromm's (1942) perspective that authentic expression arises from the freedom to write without fear of judgment. Taylor's (1992) idea of authenticity as a social ethic resonates with my belief that writing should respect the audience's perspective while staying true to the writer's voice.

Feedback, in particular, serves as a dynamic tool for growth. When I've received insightful feedback, it has often revealed dimensions of my writing I hadn't considered, ultimately making my work stronger. This aligns with Park's (2007) argument that feedback fosters not just technical improvements but also personal development as a writer.

Conclusion

Writing is a multifaceted process where purpose provides direction, authenticity ensures integrity, and feedback facilitates refinement. These principles are not only theoretical but also deeply practical, as I've experienced in my own work and teaching. Educators must guide students to define their goals, embrace their unique voices, and view feedback as an opportunity for growth.

By fostering these elements, we create a culture of writing that is purposeful, authentic, and continuously evolving—one where every writer, whether novice or experienced, can find their voice and connect meaningfully with their audience.

³ Park, James Leonard (2007). *Becoming More Authentic: The Positive Side of Existentialism* (5th ed.). Existential Books. ISBN 978-0-89231-105-7.

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